

Metadata Examples for Instrument PIDs

VERSION 1.0

Guidance Document

PID4NFDI

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Imprint

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About

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1. Introduction

Context and Scope

The purpose of this document is to provide detailed, human-readable guidance on how to map metadata collected for research instruments to the metadata required for registering a persistent identifier (PID) for instruments.

The overall aim is to promote completeness and high-quality instrument metadata within PID records. Instruments should be described in a consistent and standardized manner using rich and complete PID metadata. This supports discovery and reuse, which are essential for researchers, and enables the reliable collection, comparison, and aggregation of information across organizations and PID providers.

Before registering instruments with PIDs, several essential considerations should be addressed, as outlined in the FAIR-IMPACT user guidelines. These include identifying the authority responsible for PID registration, determining which domain-specific and institution-specific standards apply, and defining an appropriate versioning strategy for PID assignment ¹.

In addition, this guidance recommends that, wherever possible, all research outputs and entities connected to an instrument are assigned globally unique identifiers (GUIDs) at a minimum, and persistent identifiers in the best case, as described in later sections of this document. Similarly, terminology used in instrument descriptions should, where applicable, follow established community vocabularies to support semantic consistency and interoperability.

The “[Metadata Schema for the Persistent Identification of Instruments](#)” (PIDINST Metadata Schema) was a major output of the Research Data Alliance’s PIDINST Working Group (WG). As a result of this work, PID registration for instruments has been adopted by several infrastructures, including:

- [The EUDAT Collaborative Data Infrastructure](#): In collaboration with the ePIC Consortium and DataCite, EUDAT has developed the [B2INST platform](#) which enables researchers to register ePIC PIDs for instruments following the structure defined by the PIDINST Metadata Schema.

¹ Nordling, J. et al. (2025). D3.2 - User guidelines on EOSC PID implementation. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15081434>, pp. 50-1.

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- **DataCite:** From version 4.5 of the [DataCite Metadata Schema](#) onwards, “Instrument” has been included as a [resourceTypeGeneral](#) enabling the registration of DataCite Digital Object Identifiers (DOIs) for instruments. To support this, the [DataCite Metadata Work Group](#) has developed a [mapping](#) between the PIDINST Metadata Schema and DataCite Metadata Schemas.

This document builds on the core metadata profile for instruments defined by the PIDINST Metadata Schema, as directly implemented by B2INST, together with the published mapping between PIDINST and the DataCite Metadata Schema. It further expands on these resources by providing interpretations and concrete examples for individual metadata fields.

The current version of this document has not yet undergone formal review by the PIDINST Working Group. A revised version will be released following completion of that review.

Document Structure

Chapter 1 establishes the foundation for the document by defining the purpose and scope of the guidelines.

Chapter 2 presents a set of core metadata fields that are commonly used to describe research instruments. For each field, examples and explanatory notes are provided. This chapter focuses on instrument description and is independent of how the metadata is captured or represented within PID records.

Chapter 3 then addresses how typical instrument metadata can be mapped to existing PID metadata schemas, specifically the PIDINST Metadata Schema and the DataCite Metadata Schema. Chapter 3 also provides a high-level mapping of the typical instrument metadata fields introduced in Chapter 2 to:

- properties in the PIDINST Metadata Schema, including B2INST community extensions where applicable, and
- corresponding elements in the DataCite Metadata Schema.

The mapping starts from the typical metadata properties and assigns them to the relevant fields in each schema. As such, this chapter is relevant to both DataCite and B2INST users.

Chapters 3.4 build on this by presenting a detailed, property-level mapping of the DataCite Metadata Schema to the typical instrument metadata described in Chapter 2. This chapter places particular emphasis on the DataCite Metadata Schema because, unlike the PIDINST schema, it is domain-agnostic and therefore requires additional guidance when applied to a specific resource type such as instruments. This section also responds directly to a need identified by the PIDINST Working Group, which explicitly requested guidance on how to apply the DataCite Metadata Schema to instrument PIDs ². The mapping in this chapter starts from DataCite metadata properties and links them back to typical instrument metadata, hence, it is especially relevant for DataCite users.

Finally, Chapter 3.5 complements Chapter 3.4 by providing XML examples that illustrate the use of the DataCite Metadata Schema for describing instruments.

² PIDINST Github <https://github.com/rdawg-pidinst/schema/blob/master/schema-datacite.rst>: "As mentioned above, some of the definitions in the DataCite schema need to be significantly stretched in order to squeeze the relevant metadata for instruments in. It is not obvious what piece of information should be put where. It seems that some sort of a dedicated handbook on how to correctly create instrument metadata using this schema will be needed. The existing general DataCite documentation will not be enough."

2. Instrument Metadata

The registration of PIDs for instruments via DataCite and B2INST is still at an early stage. Consequently, relatively few examples of registered instrument metadata are currently available. At the time of writing this guide, 1,212 instruments are [registered with DataCite](#) and 2,390 [with B2INST](#). Among these records, only a small subset can be considered to exhibit high-quality and comprehensive metadata, as the community is still in the process of developing, refining, and adopting best practices for instrument description.

With this context in mind, the following DataCite instrument metadata record, as displayed in DataCite Commons, has been selected as a reference example for all metadata illustrations used throughout the remainder of this document:

- <http://commons.datacite.org/doi.org/10.71929/rubin/2561361>

It should be noted that certain details of the instrument metadata presented in this document differ from those in the registered DOI record. In particular, to better demonstrate metadata completeness and good practice, the example has been enriched with real information about the instrument obtained through additional research. These enhancements are intended solely for illustrative purposes.

Tables 1-3 below present a set of properties that may serve as metadata for instruments, together with illustrative examples. The metadata listed in these tables are independent of any specific PID metadata schema or serialization format.

For clarity and readability, the metadata properties are grouped into three broad categories:

1. Information describing the instrument itself,
2. Contextual information, and
3. Organizational information.

Not all metadata properties are expected to be equally relevant for every instrument. The applicability and importance of individual properties will vary depending on the instrument type, as well as on whether the instrument is used in a laboratory environment or for in situ observations in the field.

2.1 Instrument Information

Metadata property	Example	Comments
Manufacturer of the instrument	SLAC National Accelerator Laboratory NSF-DOE Vera C. Rubin Observatory	
Name of the instrument	LSST Commissioning Camera	The name by which the instrument is known. Ideally should include the model name, but may also include a name designated by the organization.
model of the instrument	LSSTComCam	The full model or version designation of the instrument. Instruments may undergo upgrades or modular extensions over time, which should be reflected where relevant.
Identifiers assigned to the instrument	OSTI ID: 2561361	A unique identifier associated with the instrument, such as a serial number, organizational inventory identifier, or an equivalent internal or external identifier.

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Metadata property	Example	Comments
Type of the instrument	Digital Camera	Where possible, values should be taken from a standard or controlled vocabulary.
Dimensions of the instrument, including units, and error ranges	Length: 1.4 m Diameter: 0.75 m	
Weight of the instrument, including units	290 kg	
Photographs/diagrams of the instrument	https://noirlab.edu/public/images/rubin-32339965357-47a5316340-o/	This information may already be embedded in local sample or dataset metadata, but should ideally be linked explicitly, for example via URLs.
Variables measured by the instrument	Optical radiance	
Other important terms that distinguish the instrument	Falls under DOE OSTI E-Link subject 79 ASTRONOMY AND ASTROPHYSICS	Any additional descriptive information that helps to characterize or distinguish the instrument beyond the core metadata properties.

Table 1: Instrument metadata related to the instrument instance itself.

2.2 Contextual Information

Metadata property	Example	Comments
Site where the instrument is located, including the type of site	Cerro Pachon, Chile	Depending on the instrument type, it may be housed within a facility or deployed at a specific site for in situ observations.
Precise location of the instrument, including its elevation/altitude	-30.244639, -70.749417	Some location information may already be captured above. However, for instruments used in situ, precise geographic coordinates (e.g., latitude and longitude) may be required. Elevation should be provided relative to sea level, or another clearly defined reference point.
Environmental conditions at the site location	Not applicable, kept in a controlled environment	In cases where environmental conditions may affect observations or analyses, relevant information should be recorded.

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Metadata property	Example	Comments
Technical description of the instrument and its capabilities	<p>The LSST Commissioning Camera (LSSTComCam) was mounted on the Simonyi Survey Telescope in August 2022 and observed for seven weeks in late 2024 until it was removed from the telescope in December 2024. It is a smaller, fully functional version of LSSTCam, with only the central raft of 9 4k x 4k CCDs (all ITL sensors) and comprising 144 megapixels. Every CCD has 16 amplifiers, each reading 1 million pixels. LSSTComCam was designed to enable end-to-end testing of the observatory's systems, including data acquisition, image processing, and observatory operations.</p> <p>Language: English</p>	<p>This field may include, for example:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • technical specifications of the instrument, • variables measured or observed, • formats of instrument outputs, • calibration parameters and tolerances, • supported operating languages, • and other relevant technical characteristics.
Software used by the instrument, including the URL and version	Custom built as part of the LSST Science Platform	Information about installed software and versions. This is particularly important when multiple software configurations are possible or when software can be upgraded. Where available, the software itself should ideally be identified using a PID.
Date when the instrument PID was registered	2024	The date on which the PID was issued for the instrument. This typically occurs some time after the instrument has been purchased, built, or installed.

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Metadata property	Example	Comments
When the instrument was purchased/setup/installed, and its state at this time	August 2022	Indicates the age of the instrument. “State” refers to whether the instrument was new, used, reconditioned, or otherwise modified at the time of purchase, setup, or installation.
When the instrument last underwent maintenance, including if it was removed from operation	Removed from telescope in Dec 2024	
Timestamps of instrument usage	24 Oct to 11 Dec 2024	Relevant when the instrument is active only during specific periods, for example when collecting time-series observations.
Related instruments	Simonyi Survey Telescope	Indicates whether the instrument is part of a larger system or composed of sub-instruments. This is especially important when parent or child instruments are themselves registered with PIDs.
Research outputs/entities that are connected with/resulted from the instrument	Paper/presentation describing the LSST Commissioning Camera: https://doi.org/10.1117/12.2630184	References to datasets, publications, or other research outputs produced using the instrument. This information should be updated over time as new outputs are

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Metadata property	Example	Comments
	Data collected by the LSST Commissioning Camera: https://doi.org/10.71929/rubin/2570308 Replaced by Full LSST Cam: https://doi.org/10.71929/rubin/2571927	generated, particularly when those outputs are registered with PIDs.

Table 2: Instrument metadata related to the instrument's context.

2.3 Organizational Information

Metadata property	Example	Comments
Project that the instrument was purchased/built for	Legacy Survey of Space and Time (LSST) project	The associated project should ideally be identified using a PID.
Individuals/organizations responsible for the instrument	SLAC National Accelerator Laboratory NSF-DOE Vera C. Rubin Observatory	The organization(s) or individual(s) that effectively act as the instrument owner.

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Metadata property	Example	Comments
Individuals/organizations involved in the maintenance/management of the instrument and their roles	SLAC National Accelerator Laboratory NSF-DOE Vera C. Rubin Observatory	All collaborators involved in the instrument’s lifecycle, together with their respective roles and responsibilities.
Organization/repository responsible for the instrument PID/metadata	SLAC National Accelerator Laboratory	Identifies the entity responsible for publishing, maintaining, and updating the PID metadata.
Funding agencies who provided finance for the instrument	USDOE Office of Science (SC), High Energy Physics (HEP) Grant #: AC02-76SF00515 National Science Foundation Grant #: AST-1258333	Funding sources should be listed, ideally including award or grant identifiers.
Current status of the instrument	Decommissioned in Dec 2024	Indicates whether the instrument is operational. If not, the date at which operation ceased should be recorded.
Embargos on publishing information about the instrument or obtaining access to the instrument	While the instrument was installed in 2022, it was not made available for operation until 2024	Although this information may not be directly captured in PID metadata, it influences when a PID record can be published or made publicly accessible.
Who can access/use the instrument	Access is only by authorized laboratory staff	Clear information about access conditions and eligibility is essential to support potential reuse.

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Metadata property	Example	Comments
Any sensitivities concerning release of information	None	Not intended for direct capture, but useful for determining whether certain information should be excluded, restricted, or anonymized.

Table 3: Instrument metadata related to organizational information about the instrument.

3. Mappings

This section describes how the instrument metadata properties introduced in the previous section can be mapped to existing PID metadata schemas. Specifically, it addresses mappings to:

- a) the PIDINST metadata schema, as implemented by B2INST, including the use of community extensions where applicable, and
- b) the DataCite Metadata Schema.

To illustrate these mappings and maintain continuity with earlier examples, the instrument metadata examples introduced above are mapped in Table 4 to the corresponding PIDINST/B2INST metadata properties (column two) and DataCite metadata properties (column three).

B2INST directly adopts the PIDINST Metadata Schema but additionally supports the definition and use of community extensions. These extensions can be used when the PIDINST schema does not provide sufficiently expressive metadata fields to capture instrument-specific requirements for a particular use case. Accordingly, in column two of Table 4, each example metadata property is either mapped to an existing PIDINST metadata field or, where appropriate, a recommendation is made to introduce a community extension.

Column three of Table 4 presents the corresponding mappings to the DataCite Metadata Schema. These mappings are further elaborated in Chapter 3.4, which provides more detailed guidance and concrete examples. In addition, Chapter 3.5 presents complete XML examples with annotations to illustrate the practical application of the DataCite Metadata Schema for describing instruments.

Please note that some of the content presented in Tables 4, 5, and 6 extends beyond the recommendations currently provided by PIDINST and DataCite for the use of the DataCite Metadata Schema in the context of instruments. To make such cases explicit, the following notational conventions are used throughout Tables 4, 5 and 6 to indicate deviations from, or extensions to, existing recommendations.

- **New interpretation of metadata properties (*):** If a metadata property in the DataCite Metadata Schema is marked with an asterisk (*), this indicates either that no guidance has yet been provided by DataCite or PIDINST on how to apply this property to instruments (for example, the Rights property), or that the property is typically interpreted differently for other resource

types (for example, Size, which in this context refers to the physical size of an instrument rather than the file size of a digital object).

- **Deviations from PIDINST/DataCite mapping (**):** If a metadata property in the DataCite Metadata Schema is marked with a double asterisk (**), this indicates that the recommended usage in this document deviates from the official PIDINST or DataCite mapping recommendations.
- **Whenever * or ** is applied to a metadata property,** a corresponding footnote is provided with additional details and discussion points. Proposed new interpretations and deviations will be discussed with the PIDINST Working Group with the aim of aligning and refining future recommendations.

Ordering of Properties: In some cases, multiple PIDINST or DataCite metadata properties are associated with a single instrument metadata property. For example, the instrument metadata property “Model of the instrument” may be mapped to **Model**, **Name**, and **Description** in the PIDINST schema (column two). In such cases, the first listed property (here, **Model**) represents the primary field designated to capture the instrument metadata property. The additional listed fields (here, **Name** and **Description**) may also contain relevant information, alongside other descriptive content.

3.1 Instrument Information

Instrument metadata property	Properties within the PIDINST Metadata Schema where the instrument metadata may be captured; possible community extensions for B2INST additionally marked	Properties within the DataCite Metadata Schema where the instrument metadata may be captured
Manufacturer of the instrument	Manufacturer	Creator
Name of the instrument	Name	Title
Model of the instrument	Model Name Description	Title Description
Identifiers assigned to the instrument	Identifier AlternateIdentifier	Identifier AlternateIdentifier
Type of the instrument	InstrumentType Description	Description Subject ³

³ According to the [PIDINST White Paper](#), the [Subject](#) property is particularly suitable when the term used to specify the instrument type is taken from a controlled vocabulary. This is because its subproperties allow the name and URI of the vocabulary scheme, the URI of the term itself, and any associated classification codes to be recorded explicitly.

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Instrument metadata property	Properties within the PIDINST Metadata Schema where the instrument metadata may be captured; possible community extensions for B2INST additionally marked	Properties within the DataCite Metadata Schema where the instrument metadata may be captured
	Name	ResourceType** 4 Title
Dimensions of the instrument, including units, and error ranges	Description B2INST community extension	Size* 5
Weight of the instrument, including units and error ranges	Description B2INST community extension	Size* 5
Photographs/diagrams of the instrument	RelatedIdentifier	RelatedIdentifier
Variables measured by the instrument	MeasuredVariable	Description

⁴ The PIDINST Working Group does not further constrain the general definition of the resourceType field for instruments (“the type of the resource”), leaving its interpretation largely open. However, the suggested values provided in the mapping table (“Platform”, “Instrument”, and “Sensor”) indicate that specifying the instrument type is at least a valid and intended use of this metadata field.

⁵ The PIDINST documentation mentions size and weight only as examples of instrument characteristics that may be presented on a [landing page](#), but does not provide explicit guidance on how the DataCite [Size](#) property should be used for instruments.

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Instrument metadata property	Properties within the PIDINST Metadata Schema where the instrument metadata may be captured; possible community extensions for B2INST additionally marked	Properties within the DataCite Metadata Schema where the instrument metadata may be captured
Other important terms that distinguish the instrument	B2INST community extension	Subject

Table 4: Mapping of instrument information metadata properties to the PIDINST/B2INST Metadata Schema and the DataCite Metadata Schema. The mapping starts from general instrument metadata properties and relates them to the corresponding fields in each schema. Please refer to the text immediately preceding the table for an explanation of the * and ** notation used throughout.

3.2 Contextual information

Instrument Metadata Property	Properties Within the PIDINST Metadata Schema Where the Instrument Metadata May Be Captured; Possible Community Extensions for B2INST additionally marked	Properties Within the DataCite Metadata Schema Where the Instrument Metadata May Be Captured
Site where the instrument is located, including the type of site	B2INST community extension ⁶	GeoLocation* ⁶

⁶ Examples for community extensions: <https://b2inst.gwdg.de/communities/MetaboHUB> (Location Information) and <https://b2inst.gwdg.de/communities/Sensor.Community> (Station).

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Instrument Metadata Property	Properties Within the PIDINST Metadata Schema Where the Instrument Metadata May Be Captured; Possible Community Extensions for B2INST additionally marked	Properties Within the DataCite Metadata Schema Where the Instrument Metadata May Be Captured
Precise location of the instrument, including its elevation/altitude	B2INST community extension ⁷	GeoLocation* ⁷ Description
Environmental conditions at the site location	B2INST community extension* ⁸	Description
Technical description of the instrument and its capabilities	Description	Description
Software used by the instrument, including the URL and version	RelatedIdentifier Description B2INST community extension* ⁹	RelatedIdentifier Description* ¹⁰

⁷ Examples for community extensions: <https://b2inst.gwdg.de/communities/ACTRIS-CIS> (Location Information) and <https://b2inst.gwdg.de/communities/Sensor.Community> (Location).

⁸ Example for a community extension: <https://b2inst.gwdg.de/communities/Sensor.Community> (Environment, Sensor Location Relative To Traffic, Short Description of Location).

⁹ Example for a community extension: <https://b2inst.gwdg.de/communities/MetaboHUB> (Software information).

¹⁰ The PIDINST Working Group has not yet addressed how information about an instrument's software should be represented in the metadata.

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Instrument Metadata Property	Properties Within the PIDINST Metadata Schema Where the Instrument Metadata May Be Captured; Possible Community Extensions for B2INST additionally marked	Properties Within the DataCite Metadata Schema Where the Instrument Metadata May Be Captured
Date when the instrument PID was minted	Date	PublicationYear
When the instrument was purchased/setup/installed, and its state at this time	Date	Date
When the instrument last underwent maintenance, including if it was removed from operation	Date	Date
Timestamps of instrument usage	Date	Date
Related instruments	RelatedIdentifier	RelatedIdentifier

Table 5: Mapping of instrument contextual information metadata properties to the PIDINST/B2INST Metadata Schema and the DataCite Metadata Schema. The mapping starts from general instrument metadata properties and relates them to the corresponding fields in each schema. Please refer to the text immediately preceding the table for an explanation of the * and ** notation used throughout.

3.3 Organizational Information

Instrument Metadata Property	Properties Within the PIDINST Metadata Schema Where the Instrument Metadata May Be Captured; Possible Community Extensions for B2INST additionally marked	Properties Within the DataCite Metadata Schema Where the Instrument Metadata May Be Captured
Project that the instrument was purchased/built for	RelatedIdentifier B2INST community extension	RelatedIdentifier Description
Individuals/organizations responsible for the instrument	Owner	Contributor
Individuals/organizations involved in the maintenance/management of the instrument and their roles	Owner	Contributor
Organization/repository responsible for the instrument PID/metadata	B2INST community extension	Publisher
Funding agencies who provided finance for the instrument	RelatedIdentifier B2INST community extension	FundingReference

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Instrument Metadata Property	Properties Within the PIDINST Metadata Schema Where the Instrument Metadata May Be Captured; Possible Community Extensions for B2INST additionally marked	Properties Within the DataCite Metadata Schema Where the Instrument Metadata May Be Captured
Research outputs/entities that are connected with/resulted from the instrument	RelatedIdentifier	RelatedIdentifier
Current status of the instrument	Date Description B2INST community extension ¹¹	Date Description
Embargos on publishing information about the instrument or obtaining access to the instrument	Date B2INST community extension	Date Rights* ¹²
Who can access/use the instrument	B2INST community extension	Rights* ¹²
Any sensitivities concerning release of information	No specific property, but could affect a number of them	No specific property, but could affect a number of them

¹¹ Example for a community extension: <https://b2inst.gwdg.de/communities/EISCAT> (Status Description).

¹² The topic of access rights has not been discussed in any of the PIDINST publications, nor do they include recommendations for using the DataCite property **Rights**.

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Table 6: Mapping of instrument organizational information metadata properties to the PIDINST/B2INST Metadata Schema and the DataCite Metadata Schema. The mapping starts from general instrument metadata properties and relates them to the corresponding fields in each schema. Please refer to the text immediately preceding the table for an explanation of the * and ** notation used throughout.

3.4 Full Mapping from Instrument Metadata to DataCite Metadata Schema

Table 7 lists each DataCite Metadata Schema property alongside the corresponding instrument metadata and provides an explanation of how each property should be applied when describing instruments. The properties are not ordered according to the sequence used in the official schema documentation. Instead, they are grouped by obligation level, with mandatory properties listed first, followed by recommended and optional properties. As shown in Table 7, the obligation level of each DataCite metadata property is indicated in column 1 and encoded as mandatory (m), recommended (r), or optional (o).

While PID metadata should ideally be as complete as possible, for example, to establish clear provenance and support accurate interpretation of data collected by instruments, it is also recognized that practical constraints may require prioritization. This approach supports the collection of essential instrument metadata needed to populate the most important DataCite metadata properties, while allowing for incremental enrichment over time

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DataCite metadata property	Relevant types of instrument metadata	Comments on DataCite property usage	Related B2INST/ PIDINST metadata properties
Identifier (m)	Identifiers assigned to the instrument	<p>An instrument will automatically be assigned a DOI prefix and suffix when it is registered with DataCite. The automatically assigned suffix will be an opaque, random string, following DOI best practices. However, because instruments are physical objects that are handled by humans, they may already have human-readable local identifiers. Encoding your locally unique identifiers into a DOI prefix and adding the DOI suffix has the power to turn them into globally unique identifiers.</p> <p>Therefore, depending on your needs, you may keep the random string or customise the suffix to match the existing identifier.</p>	Identifier
Creator (m)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Manufacturer of the instrument 	<p>The creator of an instrument is generally considered to be its manufacturer or developer. In the case of custom-built instruments, this may also be the instrument's owner.</p>	Manufacturer
Title (m)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Name of the instrument • Model of the instrument • Type of the instrument 	<p>An appropriate title is essential for the discovery and clear identification of an instrument. Typically, the title corresponds to the instrument name. However, it is recommended to include additional descriptive elements, such as the model and</p>	Name

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DataCite metadata property	Relevant types of instrument metadata	Comments on DataCite property usage	Related B2INST/ PIDINST metadata properties
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> (Other relevant information from the instrument metadata) 	instrument type , to support effective differentiation from similar instruments.	
Publisher (m)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Organization/ repository responsible for the instrument PID/metadata 	The organization registering the PID for an instrument and managing its metadata may be the instrument's legal owner, its operator, or the entity providing access to the instrument.	B2INST community extension
PublicationYear (m)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Year of issuing the instrument PID 	For the publication year, it is recommended to use the year in which the DOI was issued.	Date
ResourceType (m)**	Type of the instrument	For instruments, the resourceTypeGeneral property must be set to "Instrument" . In addition, a term may be included in the free-text resourceType property to support discovery and to help users distinguish between specific types of instruments (see Footnote 4).	InstrumentType
Subject (r)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Type of the instrument 	Wherever possible, properties describing an instrument or its context should follow relevant community or disciplinary	InstrumentType

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DataCite metadata property	Relevant types of instrument metadata	Comments on DataCite property usage	Related B2INST/ PIDINST metadata properties
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Other important terms that distinguish the instrument 	controlled vocabularies. In such cases, the controlled vocabulary term, together with the name and URI of the classification scheme, should be recorded using the Subject property.	
Contributor (r)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Individuals/ organizations responsible for the instrument Individuals/ organizations involved in the maintenance/ management of the instrument and their roles 	All individuals and organizations involved in the instrument's management across its lifecycle, from commissioning to decommissioning, should be recorded as contributors. Each contributor must be assigned a contributorType selected from the controlled vocabulary defined in the DataCite Metadata Schema. If no suitable term exists to describe a specific role, the value "Other" should be used. This property is primarily used to capture the owner of the instrument, in which case contributorType should be set to "HostingInstitution".	Owner

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DataCite metadata property	Relevant types of instrument metadata	Comments on DataCite property usage	Related B2INST/ PIDINST metadata properties
Date (r)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • When the instrument was purchased/setup/ installed, and its state at this time • When the instrument last underwent maintenance, including if it was removed from operation • Timestamps of instrument usage • Current status of the instrument • Embargos on publishing information about the instrument or obtaining access to the instrument 	<p>All significant events related to the instrument should be recorded within the Date property. The dateType and dateInformation subproperties should be used to specify the nature of the event (from a controlled list) and to provide additional contextual information.</p> <p>Key events typically include the start of operation (for example, dateType = "Other" with dateInformation = "Commissioned") and the end of operation (dateType = "Other" with dateInformation = "Decommissioned"). Where relevant, the current operational status of the instrument should also be indicated. Periods of instrument usage, such as those associated with time-series observations, may be captured using dateType = "Coverage".</p>	Date

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DataCite metadata property	Relevant types of instrument metadata	Comments on DataCite property usage	Related B2INST/ PIDINST metadata properties
RelatedIdentifier (r)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Related instruments • Project that the instrument was purchased/built for • Research outputs/entities that are connected with/resulted from the instrument • Photographs/ diagrams of the instrument • Software used by the instrument, including the URL and version 	<p>Where possible all research outputs and entities related to an instrument, whether they provide contextual information, describe the instrument itself, or result from instrument-based observations or analyses, should be registered with globally unique identifiers, and ideally persistent identifiers.</p> <p>This includes parent instruments (larger systems of which the instrument is a part) as well as child instruments (component instruments). Such relationships are recorded using the RelatedIdentifier property, which specifies the relationship type and links the instrument to the related entity via its identifier. The use of RelatedIdentifier is strongly recommended and should be maintained over time as new related entities are created, if applicable.</p> <p>Common relationType values relevant to instruments and their use are discussed in a separate publication ¹³.</p>	RelatedIdentifier B2INST community extension

¹³ Böhm, J. (2025). Linking Instrument PIDs With Related Research Entities: Guidance Document (1.0). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17535290>

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DataCite metadata property	Relevant types of instrument metadata	Comments on DataCite property usage	Related B2INST/ PIDINST metadata properties
Description (r)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Type of the instrument • Model of the instrument • Variables measured by the instrument • Precise location of the instrument, including its elevation/altitude • Environmental conditions at the site location • Technical description of the instrument and its capabilities • Software used by the instrument, including the URL and version 	<p>The free-text Description property is used to capture additional information about an instrument that is not represented elsewhere in the DataCite Metadata Schema. The mandatory descriptionType subproperty must be selected from a controlled list. The most important descriptionType values for instrument discovery and differentiation are:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Abstract: A technical overview of the instrument and its capabilities, including associated software. This may also include information about the project context and details of instrument usage, such as environmental conditions at the instrument's location. 2. TechnicalInfo: Detailed technical information about the instrument, for example input and output characteristics. Information about the current status of the instrument may also be included here if it is not captured elsewhere. 	<p>Description Model InstrumentType Measured Variables B2INST community extension</p>

Metadata Examples for Instrument PIDs: Guidance Document

DataCite metadata property	Relevant types of instrument metadata	Comments on DataCite property usage	Related B2INST/ PIDINST metadata properties
	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• Project that the instrument was purchased/built for• Current status of the instrument		

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DataCite metadata property	Relevant types of instrument metadata	Comments on DataCite property usage	Related B2INST/ PIDINST metadata properties
GeoLocation (r)*	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Site where the instrument is located, including the type of site • Precise location of the instrument (not including its elevation/altitude) 	<p>The use of the GeoLocation property depends on whether the instrument is housed within a facility or deployed in the field to conduct in situ observations. In the former case, highly precise location information is often unnecessary. In contrast, for field-based instruments, it is strongly recommended to record the instrument’s location using the GeoLocation property as accurately as possible, while taking care not to disclose sensitive information.</p> <p>The GeoLocation subproperties support different ways of representing location information, including points, boxes, places, and polygons. Among these, geoLocationPlace is the most flexible, as it allows free-text descriptions, and should be provided at a minimum.</p> <p>It should be noted that the GeoLocation property does not support recording elevation or altitude. Where relevant, this information should instead be captured using the Description property.</p>	B2INST community extension

Metadata Examples for Instrument PIDs: Guidance Document

DataCite metadata property	Relevant types of instrument metadata	Comments on DataCite property usage	Related B2INST/ PIDINST metadata properties
Language (o)* ¹⁴	Primary language in which the instrument is setup in	If an instrument has been built or configured to operate in a specific language , this information may be recorded here.	B2INST community extension
AlternatIdentifier (o)	Identifiers assigned to the instrument	As discussed earlier, instruments often already have one or more locally assigned identifiers , such as serial numbers or organizational inventory identifiers. Any additional identifiers that exist for an instrument, particularly those that support discovery or differentiation, should be recorded using the AlternatIdentifier property. A brief description of the identifier type should be provided using alternatIdentifierType. At a minimum, the value “Local” is recommended when the identifier has been assigned by an individual, organization, or research project.	AlternatIdentifier
Size (o)*	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Dimensions of the instrument, including units 	This property may be used to capture the physical dimensions of an instrument, including its weight . Measurement units should be included in all cases.	Description B2INST community extension

¹⁴ The PIDINST working group did not comment on the use of the DataCite 'Language' property for instrument records, nor on how the operational language of an instrument could be included in its metadata.

Metadata Examples for Instrument PIDs: Guidance Document

DataCite metadata property	Relevant types of instrument metadata	Comments on DataCite property usage	Related B2INST/ PIDINST metadata properties
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Weight of the instrument, including units 		
Format (o)	–	This property is typically not used for instruments.	–
Version (o)* ¹⁵	Version of the instrument	If an instrument undergoes significant upgrades over time, it is recommended to register a new PID for the updated version. The earlier and updated instrument records can then be linked using the RelatedIdentifier property.	B2INST community extension
Rights (o)*	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Embargos on publishing information about the instrument or obtaining access to the instrument Who can access/use the instrument 	Access conditions for the instrument, including any restrictions and contact information for access requests, should be recorded here.	Date B2INST community extension

¹⁵ None of the PIDINST documents addresses how to use the DataCite property 'Version'.

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DataCite metadata property	Relevant types of instrument metadata	Comments on DataCite property usage	Related B2INST/ PIDINST metadata properties
FundingReference (o)	Funding agencies that provided financial or in-kind support for the instrument	If the instrument was acquired, built, or maintained using grant funding or other financial support, information about the relevant funding agencies should be recorded.	RelatedIdentifier B2INST community extension
RelatedItem (o)	–	<p>This property is typically not used for instruments.</p> <p>While this property may be applicable in certain cases, readers are encouraged to consult the most recent version of the DataCite Metadata Schema documentation and determine whether its use is appropriate.</p>	–

Table 7: Mapping of DataCite Metadata Schema properties to typical instrument metadata from Chapter 2. Column 1 indicates the obligation level of each property, mandatory (m), recommended (r), or optional (o). Empty cells in the PIDINST column reflect the mapping direction, as some DataCite properties do not have corresponding PIDINST fields. The * and ** notation is explained in the text preceding Table 4.

3.5. Full Annotated XML

This section concludes the document by presenting the complete DataCite Metadata Schema record for the research instrument example used throughout this guidance. It builds on the XML snippets introduced in Chapter 3.4 and provides a fully annotated example in which each metadata property is explained in terms of its relevance to research instruments and the information it captures. The example is intended to serve as a practical reference for creating comprehensive and well-structured instrument metadata, supporting consistency, interoperability, and the discoverability and reuse of instrument-related data in line with community best practices.

```
<?xml version="1.0" encoding="UTF-8"?>
<resource
  xmlns="http://datacite.org/schema/kernel-4"
  xmlns:xsi="http://www.w3.org/2001/XMLSchema-instance"
  xsi:schemaLocation="http://datacite.org/schema/kernel-4
http://schema.datacite.org/meta/kernel-4/metadata.xsd">
  <!--
Identifier:
The DOI for the instrument, formed from a 10. prefix and a
suffix.
The suffix is customizable and in this case matches an existing
DOE OSTI identifier assigned to the instrument,
plus an additional code connected to the instrument owner.
-->
  <identifier
identifierType="DOI">10.71929/RUBIN/2561361</identifier>
  <!--
Creators:
The instrument has been custom built in-house, and therefore
Creator matches the instrument owners.
A globally unique identifier for the organization should be
included in nameIdentifier whenever available.
```

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Used for citation purposes.

```
-->
<creators>
  <creator>
    <creatorName nameType="Organizational">SLAC National
Accelerator Laboratory</creatorName>
    <nameIdentifier nameIdentifierScheme="ROR"
schemeURI="https://ror.org/">https://ror.org/05gzmn429</nameIde
ntifier>
  </creator>
  <creator>
    <creatorName nameType="Organizational">NSF-DOE Vera C.
Rubin Observatory</creatorName>
    <nameIdentifier nameIdentifierScheme="ROR"
schemeURI="https://ror.org/">https://ror.org/048g3cy84</nameIde
ntifier>
  </creator>
</creators>
```

<!--

Titles:

An appropriate title is vital for discovery and distinction. Here, Title follows the standard practice of using the instrument name.

The abbreviated version of the instrument name can be added as an alternative title.

```
-->
<titles>
  <title xml:lang="en">LSST Commissioning Camera</title>
  <title xml:lang="en"
titleType="AlternativeTitle">LSSTComCam</title>
</titles>
<!--
```

Publisher:

In this case, the organization registering the PID for the

Metadata Examples for Instrument PIDs: Guidance Document

instrument is the legal owner.

A globally unique identifier for the organization should be included whenever available.

-->

<publisher

publisherIdentifier="https://ror.org/05gzmn429"

publisherIdentifierScheme="ROR"

schemeURI="https://ror.org/"

xml:lang="en">SLAC National Accelerator

Laboratory</publisher>

<!--

PublicationYear:

The year when the DOI for the instrument was registered.

Used for citation purposes.

-->

<publicationYear>2024</publicationYear>

<!--

ResourceType:

Terminology that differentiates the type of instrument.

The resourceTypeGeneral property for an instrument is always "Instrument".

-->

<resourceType resourceTypeGeneral="Instrument">Digital
Camera</resourceType>

<!--

Subjects:

Keywords from standard vocabularies that describe the instrument or its context.

The classification scheme and its URI should be captured whenever possible.

-->

<subjects>

<subject

schemeURI="https://www.osti.gov/elink/authorities/subject"

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```
xml:lang="en">79 ASTRONOMY AND ASTROPHYSICS</subject>
</subjects>

<!--
Contributors:
Individuals and organizations involved in the instrument's
management workflow.
Unless included in Creator, those listed do not form part of
the instrument's citation.
A globally unique identifier for the person/organization should
be included in nameIdentifier whenever available.
Contributor additionally includes a contributorType.
-->
<contributors>
  <contributor contributorType="HostingInstitution">
    <contributorName nameType="Organizational">SLAC National
Accelerator Laboratory</contributorName>
    <nameIdentifier nameIdentifierScheme="ROR"
schemeURI="https://ror.org/">https://ror.org/05gzmn429</nameIde
ntifier>
  </contributor>
  <contributor contributorType="HostingInstitution">
    <contributorName nameType="Organizational">NSF-DOE Vera C.
Rubin Observatory</contributorName>
    <nameIdentifier nameIdentifierScheme="ROR"
schemeURI="https://ror.org/">https://ror.org/048g3cy84</nameIde
ntifier>
  </contributor>
</contributors>
<!--
Dates:
Important events related to the instrument are logged here
(e.g., commissioned/decommissioned, periods of use).
dateType records the event type; dateInformation captures
```

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additional detail when needed.

```
-->
```

```
<dates>
```

```
  <date dateType="Issued">2024</date>
```

```
  <date dateType="Other"
```

```
dateInformation="Commissioned">2022-08</date>
```

```
  <date dateType="Other"
```

```
dateInformation="Decommissioned">2024-12</date>
```

```
  <date dateType="Coverage">2024-10-24/2024-12-11</date>
```

```
</dates>
```

```
<!--
```

Language:

The operational language of the instrument (or the primary language used for documentation/metadata).

```
-->
```

```
<language>en</language>
```

```
<!--
```

AlternateIdentifiers:

Local identifiers, serial numbers, or inventory numbers assigned during the lifecycle, supporting discovery/distinction.

alternateIdentifierType should describe the identifier type.

```
-->
```

```
<alternateIdentifiers>
```

```
  <alternateIdentifier alternateIdentifierType="OSTI  
ID">2561361</alternateIdentifier>
```

```
</alternateIdentifiers>
```

```
<!--
```

RelatedIdentifiers:

Links the instrument to related research outputs (and other entities) through globally unique identifiers.

relationType describes the relationship.

Good practice:

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- Use this maximally and update it regularly as relationships are formed.

- References between entities should ideally be reciprocal (i.e., the related entity should also link back when feasible).

-->

```
<relatedIdentifiers>
  <relatedIdentifier relatedIdentifierType="URL"
relationType="IsDocumentedBy"
resourceTypeGeneral="Image">https://noirlab.edu/public/images/rubin-32339965357-47a5316340-o/</relatedIdentifier>
  <relatedIdentifier relatedIdentifierType="DOI"
relationType="IsDescribedBy"
resourceTypeGeneral="ConferencePaper">10.1117/12.2630184</relatedIdentifier>
  <relatedIdentifier relatedIdentifierType="DOI"
relationType="Collects"
resourceTypeGeneral="Dataset">10.71929/rubin/2570308</relatedIdentifier>
  <relatedIdentifier relatedIdentifierType="URL"
relationType="IsPartOf"
resourceTypeGeneral="Instrument">https://noirlab.edu/public/programs/vera-c-rubin-observatory/simonyi-survey-telescope/</relatedIdentifier>
  <relatedIdentifier relatedIdentifierType="URL"
relationType="IsPartOf"
resourceTypeGeneral="Project">https://www.lsst.org/about</relatedIdentifier>
  <relatedIdentifier relatedIdentifierType="DOI"
relationType="IsPreviousVersionOf"
resourceTypeGeneral="Instrument">10.71929/rubin/2571927</relatedIdentifier>
</relatedIdentifiers>

<!--
```

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Sizes:

Dimensional properties of the instrument, including the measurement units.

-->

```
<sizes>
  <size>Length: 1.4 m</size>
  <size>Diameter: 0.75 m</size>
  <size>Weight: 290 kg</size>
</sizes>
```

<!--

Version:

Version number to differentiate between versions if the instrument is upgraded over time.

-->

```
<version>1.0</version>
```

<!--

Rights:

Access rights for the instrument and any relevant constraints.

-->

```
<rightsList>
  <rights xml:lang="en">Access to LSSTComCam is by authorized
laboratory staff only</rights>
</rightsList>
```

<!--

Descriptions:

Free-text information not captured elsewhere.

descriptionType="Abstract" is used here for a technical description of the instrument and its capabilities.

-->

```
<descriptions>
  <description xml:lang="en" descriptionType="Abstract">
```

The LSST Commissioning Camera (LSSTComCam) was mounted on the Simonyi Survey Telescope in August 2022 and observed for seven weeks in late 2024 until it was removed from the

Metadata Examples for Instrument PIDs: Guidance Document

telescope in December 2024. It is a smaller, fully functional version of LSSTCam, with only the central raft of 9 4k x 4k CCDs (all ITL sensors) and comprising 144 megapixels. Every CCD has 16 amplifiers, each reading 1 million pixels. LSSTComCam was designed to enable end-to-end testing of the observatory's systems, including data acquisition, image processing, and observatory operations.

```
</description>
```

```
</descriptions>
```

```
<!--
```

GeoLocations:

For facility-based instruments, include the general place name and (optionally) precise coordinates.

```
-->
```

```
<geoLocations>
```

```
<geoLocation>
```

```
<geoLocationPlace>Cerro Pachon, Chile</geoLocationPlace>
```

```
<geoLocationPoint>
```

```
<pointLatitude>-30.244639</pointLatitude>
```

```
<pointLongitude>-70.749417</pointLongitude>
```

```
</geoLocationPoint>
```

```
</geoLocation>
```

```
</geoLocations>
```

```
<!--
```

FundingReferences:

Funding agencies providing support for purchase/manufacture/maintenance.

Include awardNumber and a globally unique funder identifier whenever available.

```
-->
```

```
<fundingReferences>
```

```
<fundingReference>
```

```
<funderName>USDOE Office of Science (SC), High Energy
```

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```
Physics (HEP) </funderName>
  <awardNumber>AC02-76SF00515</awardNumber>
</fundingReference>
<fundingReference>
  <funderName>National Science Foundation</funderName>
  <funderIdentifier funderIdentifierType="Crossref Funder
ID">100000001</funderIdentifier>
  <awardNumber>AST-1258333</awardNumber>
</fundingReference>
</fundingReferences>
</resource>
```